

EVALUATING THE PATIENT PERCEPTIONS OF MRI SAFETY IN THE ERA OF ADVANCED IMAGING TECHNOLOGIES.

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Abstract

This descriptive cross-sectional study, conducted at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, from February to April 2025, assessed Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) safety knowledge, perceptions, and satisfaction among 101 adult patients using a structured questionnaire. MRI, a non-invasive imaging technique using magnetic fields, carries risks like projectile hazards and implant interactions, making patient awareness crucial, especially in areas with low health literacy like Rajasthan. Results showed that 57.42% of patients had high safety awareness, with urban patients (83.33%) significantly more aware than rural patients (51.81%). While gender did not significantly impact awareness levels ($\chi^2 = 0.1232$, $p = 0.7255$), females reported higher satisfaction (81.25%) with safety information than males (56.25%). The study highlights the need for targeted educational interventions, particularly in rural areas, to improve MRI safety understanding and patient satisfaction.

Keywords: MRI Safety, Patient Awareness, Patient Knowledge, Patient Satisfaction, Rural Population, Urban Population, Health Literacy, Cross-sectional Study, Rajasthan.

INTRODUCTION

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is a high-resolution cross-sectional imaging technique that provides detailed anatomical images of the human body without the use

of ionising radiation. Unlike other diagnostic imaging modalities, MRI is non-invasive and does not alter the physical structure or chemical composition of tissues, making it particularly advantageous for repeated imaging studies [1]. The basic principle of MRI involves placing the patient inside a powerful magnet, where the alignment of hydrogen protons in the body is influenced by a strong static magnetic field. When a radiofrequency (RF) pulse is applied, these protons are excited and pushed out of equilibrium. As they return to their original alignment, they emit signals that are detected by RF coils and transformed into images by the MRI computer system [2,3,4]. This imaging can be performed in any anatomical plane, offering unparalleled versatility and diagnostic clarity [5].

Several types of magnets are used in MRI systems—permanent, resistive, and superconducting—each with specific applications and limitations. Permanent magnets, typically made of alloys like iron, cobalt, and nickel, are cost-effective and well-suited for pediatric and geriatric patients due to their open design and reduced patient anxiety, though they generally operate at low magnetic field strengths of up to 0.35 Tesla [6,7]. Resistive magnets, composed of copper or aluminum coils, are more affordable and easier to maintain but generate significant heat, necessitating water-based cooling systems. They typically produce magnetic fields up to 0.5 Tesla and are useful in limited-resource settings [8,9,10]. In contrast, superconducting magnets, made of niobium-titanium alloy and cooled by cryogenic liquid helium to 4K (-269°C), can achieve field strengths up to 3.0 Tesla with high homogeneity. While they offer superior image quality, their high cost, large size, and tendency to induce claustrophobia are notable drawbacks [11,12].

RF coils play a pivotal role in MRI by transmitting RF energy and receiving the resulting signals. These coils can be surface coils, Helmholtz pairs, or birdcage coils, each designed for specific anatomical regions to enhance image resolution and signal-to-noise ratio [13,14,15]. Gradient coils further contribute to the spatial encoding of MR signals, allowing for high-resolution imaging and advanced functional studies such as diffusion-weighted imaging. However, their use can result in peripheral nerve stimulation and the generation of eddy currents, especially at ultra-high field strengths (7 Tesla and above) [16,17,18,19].

Despite these technological advancements, MRI is not without risk. The strong magnetic field can attract ferromagnetic objects, transforming them into projectiles that pose significant danger to patients and staff [20,21]. Clothing or accessories containing metallic fibers may heat up and cause burns during imaging. Patients with medical implants such as pacemakers, aneurysm clips, or cochlear implants may be exposed to life-threatening interactions with the magnetic field. Therefore, rigorous pre-screening protocols and staff training are essential to mitigate these risks [22,23]. The use of gadolinium-based contrast agents, though generally safer than iodinated agents, is not without concerns, particularly in patients with renal insufficiency or those undergoing repeated scans [24,25].

MRI safety awareness is especially crucial in settings with limited health literacy. In regions like Rajasthan, where illiteracy rates are high, many patients mistakenly perceive MRI as a treatment rather than a diagnostic modality.[26] There is also widespread

unawareness about contraindications related to metallic implants or pregnancy, despite growing evidence supporting the safety of MRI during the second and third trimesters [27,28]. The presence of anxiety, claustrophobia, and misconceptions can compromise image quality, prolong examination times, and increase patient discomfort, further emphasizing the need for pre-procedural counseling and structured educational interventions [29].

Thus, in the era of rapidly advancing imaging technologies, evaluating patient perceptions and awareness of MRI safety is essential. This study aims to identify gaps in patient knowledge, assess satisfaction levels, and explore demographic disparities to support the development of targeted education strategies and ensure safer, more informed participation in MRI procedures.[30]

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional questionnaire-based design to assess patients' knowledge, perceptions, and satisfaction related to MRI safety. It was conducted at the Radiology Department of NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan, over a period of three months, from February 2025 to April 2025. The study population comprised all patients aged 18 years and above who were referred for MRI scans during the study period. Patients with cognitive impairments, early pregnancy, metallic implants, unconscious status, or those admitted to the ICU were excluded to ensure the reliability of responses and clinical safety. A complete enumeration sampling technique was used, whereby all eligible patients undergoing MRI scans during the defined period were included, resulting in a total sample size of 101 participants. Data collection was carried out through structured face-to-face interviews using a standardized questionnaire, which covered demographic details, awareness of MRI safety protocols, and satisfaction levels. The MRI scans were performed using a SIEMENS MAGNETOM VIDA 3 Tesla scanner. This methodology ensured comprehensive data collection and reliable insights into patient awareness and perceptions of MRI safety practices.

RESULTS

A total of 101 adult patients undergoing MRI at Nims Hospital, Jaipur, participated in the study. of these, 59 (58.42%) were male and 42 (41.58%) were female, showing a slight male predominance. The majority of participants (58.49%) were in the 18–45 age group, followed by 19.81% in the 46–60 group, and 16.98% aged above 60, indicating a predominantly younger patient population. Area-wise distribution showed that 82.18% of participants resided in rural areas, while only 17.82% were from urban backgrounds. In terms of MRI safety awareness, 57.42% of the patients demonstrated high awareness, whereas 42.57% had low awareness. Notably, awareness levels were higher among urban participants, with 83.33% showing high awareness compared to 51.81% of rural residents.

Gender-wise analysis showed that 59.52% of females had high awareness compared to 55.93% of males; however, the chi-square test revealed no statistically significant association between gender and awareness level ($\chi^2 = 0.1232$, $p = 0.7255$). Satisfaction levels also varied by gender, with 81.25% of females expressing satisfaction with MRI safety information and procedures, compared to 56.25% of males. These results highlight notable disparities in awareness and satisfaction based on demographic factors such as area and gender, emphasizing the importance of targeted educational interventions.

Table 1. GENDER- WISE DISTRIBUTION

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE(%)
MALE	59	58.42%
FEMALE	42	41.58%
TOTAL	101	100%

Table 1 and the chart show a slight male predominance, with 59 males (58.42%) and 42 females (41.58%).

TABLE 2. AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE(%)
18-45	62	58.49%
46-60	21	19.81%
>60	18	16.98%
TOTAL	101	100%

Table 2 and the chart indicate that the majority (58.49%, n=62) were aged 18–45, followed by 19.81% (n=21) aged 46–60, and 16.98% (n=18) over 60.

TABLE 3. AREA WISE DISTRIBUTION

AREA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE(%)
RURAL	83	82.18%
URBAN	18	17.82%
TOTAL	101	100%

Table 3 and the chart highlight a predominantly rural sample, with 83 patients (82.18%) from rural areas and 18 (17.82%) from urban areas

TABLE 4: AREA VS AWARENESS DISTRIBUTION

AREA	AWARENESS LEVEL	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE(%)
RURAL	LOW	40	48.19%
RURAL	HIGH	43	51.81%
URBAN	LOW	03	16.67%
URBAN	HIGH	15	83.33%

Table 4 and the chart show that rural patients had balanced awareness levels (51.81% high, n=43; 48.19% low, n=40), while urban patients had higher awareness (83.33% high, n=15; 16.67% low, n=3).

Statistical Analysis

Overall, 57.42% (n=58) of patients demonstrated high awareness, and 42.57% (n=43) had low awareness. Among males (n=59), 55.93% (n=33) had high awareness, and 44.07% (n=26) had low awareness. Among females (n=42), 59.52% (n=25) had high awareness, and 40.48% (n=17) had low awareness. A Chi-Square Test of Independence ($\chi^2 = 0.1232$, $p = 0.7255$, $df = 1$) indicated no significant association between gender and awareness levels. Females reported higher satisfaction (81.25%) than males (56.25%).

DISCUSSION

This article compares two studies assessing patient knowledge and perceptions of MRI safety in Saudi Arabia. S.A Alghamdi *et al.* (2024) nationwide study, involving 446 participants across nine hospitals, revealed that 57% of patients had limited knowledge about MRI safety. While 94.2% were aware that metal objects are prohibited in MRI rooms and 78% recognized MRI as a diagnostic tool, misconceptions persisted. Notably, 80.3% incorrectly believed that MRI is unsafe during pregnancy, and 62.3% were unaware of the

need for kidney function tests when using contrast agents. Higher educational attainment and employment status were associated with better knowledge levels. Despite 86.3% of patients relying on healthcare professionals for MRI-related information, only 15.2% were very satisfied with the information provided. Additionally, 43% of patients reported experiencing anxiety during MRI scans.

In contrast, a separate thesis conducted at a single tertiary care hospital with 101 participants found that 57.42% of patients had high awareness of MRI safety, while 42.57% had low awareness. This higher awareness level could be attributed to the smaller, more homogeneous sample. The thesis also highlighted gender differences in satisfaction, with 81.25% of females and 56.25% of males reporting satisfaction with the information provided. Urban patients demonstrated higher awareness (83.33%) compared to rural patients (51.81%), suggesting that access to education and healthcare exposure plays a significant role. While the thesis did not explicitly quantify anxiety levels, it acknowledged the need to reduce anxiety and improve compliance through better education and satisfaction monitoring.

Both studies underscore the importance of targeted educational interventions, particularly for rural, less-educated, or unemployed populations, to address misconceptions and enhance patient cooperation during MRI scans. They also emphasize the necessity for healthcare providers to be trained not only in technical MRI protocols but also in effective patient communication and education to bridge knowledge gaps. While S.A Alghamdi *et.al*(2024) study provides a broad, statistically powered insight reflecting nationwide trends, the thesis offers focused, hospital-specific observations with implications for localized health education interventions. Together, these studies highlight the universal need to improve patient understanding and safety in MRI practices, which is critical for ensuring informed participation and reducing scan-related risks.

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted at Nims Hospital, Jaipur, revealed that 57.42% of patients had high MRI safety awareness, while 42.57% exhibited low awareness. Urban patients showed significantly higher awareness (83.33%) than rural patients (51.81%), suggesting disparities in health education access. Females reported higher satisfaction (81.25%) than males (56.25%), indicating potential gender-based differences in healthcare experiences. The lack of a significant association between gender and awareness ($\chi^2 = 0.1232$, $p = 0.7255$) suggests consistent awareness across genders. Targeted educational interventions, particularly in rural areas, are essential to address knowledge gaps, enhance compliance, and improve patient satisfaction in MRI procedures.

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